

Research on Moral Education Integration in Primary School English Teaching

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Abstract

Primary school English teaching plays a crucial role in cultivating students' language proficiency and comprehensive literacy, while moral education integration is the key pathway to fulfill the fundamental task of fostering virtue through education. Through literature analysis and classroom observation, this study systematically examines the current problems and causes of moral education integration in primary school English teaching. Findings reveal that teachers' insufficient attention due to utilitarian teaching orientations and monotonous implementation methods are primary issues, stemming from teachers' limited capabilities, imperfect evaluation systems, and lack of institutional safeguards. Accordingly, hierarchical strategies are proposed: Teachers should enhance moral awareness, innovate teaching methods (e.g., exploiting moral elements in textbooks, organizing English corner activities), and exemplify through actions; Schools should strengthen training, create cultural atmospheres, and improve evaluation mechanisms. The research outcomes provide a practical paradigm for integrating moral education into subject teaching, facilitating the cultivation of well-rounded talents developed morally, intellectually, physically, aesthetically, and labor-wise.

Keywords: Primary school English; English teaching; Moral education integration

1. Introduction

The Compulsory Education English Curriculum Standards (2022 Edition) states: "Compulsory education English curriculum reflects the unity of instrumentality and humanity. Learning and using English helps students understand different cultures, compare cultural similarities and differences, absorb cultural essence, gradually form awareness and ability for cross-cultural communication, learn to view the world objectively and rationally, cultivate an international perspective, nurture patriotism, strengthen cultural confidence, form correct worldviews, outlooks on life, and values, laying the foundation for students' lifelong learning and adaptation to future social development." (Ministry of Education, 2022) This clearly demonstrates that moral education holds a pivotal position in primary school English teaching and is an inseparable part of it.

However, the current state of moral education integration in primary school English teaching is unsatisfactory. On one hand, some teachers overly focus on imparting linguistic knowledge and training examination skills, neglecting the important role of moral education in English teaching. On the other hand, even when teachers recognize the importance of moral education, they often lack effective integration strategies and methods in practical implementation, resulting in poor outcomes.

The connotation of moral education encompasses two levels. Broadly, moral education includes social moral education and school moral education, among others. It refers to a series of purposeful and planned activities that exert a positive

influence on social members' political viewpoints, ideological concepts, and moral qualities. Narrowly, moral education primarily focuses on school moral education, which is the core. It involves educators, based on the needs of a specific society or class, employing more targeted and systematic methods to deeply educate and influence learners in the realms of ideology, politics, and morality (Liu,2019).

Zhang (2000) emphasizes that the essence of moral education integration lies in using scientific means to embed moral education content within specific subject knowledge, avoiding empty preaching. By leveraging the educational value inherent in scientific knowledge, it helps students subliminally form noble moral character, effectively enhancing the effectiveness and depth of moral education. The 21st Century New Concepts in Education Book indicates that the core concept of integrated education is to skillfully embed moral education into subject classroom teaching and extracurricular activities to enhance students' ideological, moral, and cultural awareness and promote their all-round development. This education touches students' hearts in an intangible way. The concept of educating through the discipline has significant meaning and value. It can effectively stimulate students' learning interest and enthusiasm, and it can decompose the content of character education into specific moral requirements, making moral education teaching more refined and comprehensive, thereby achieving better educational outcomes (Zhou&Gao,1998).

The Primary School Moral Education Outline issued in 1993 states: "To cultivate students to initially possess the ideological sentiments and good character of loving the motherland, the people, labor, science, and socialism; to develop their awareness of observing social ethics and habits of civilized behavior; laying a preliminary, sound ideological and moral foundation for them to become builders and successors of the socialist cause who are developed morally, intellectually, and physically." The report to the 20th National Congress of the Communist Party of China proposed that the fundamental task of education is fostering virtue through education. It calls for fully implementing the Party's educational policy, fulfilling the fundamental task of fostering virtue through education, and cultivating builders and successors of socialist modernization who are developed morally, intellectually, physically, aesthetically, and labor-wise (Han,2023). This demonstrates the paramount importance of moral education in the primary school stage.

English teaching comprehensively encompasses multiple dimensions, including linguistic knowledge, skill development, cultural awareness enhancement, and learning strategy guidance. The organic integration of moral education elements into these rich teaching contents adds depth and breadth. For instance, when guiding students to appreciate the unique charm of English-speaking cultures, not only is cultural knowledge imparted, but respect and tolerance for different cultures are emphasized to cultivate cross-cultural communication abilities. Simultaneously, when discussing social issues, students are encouraged to deeply observe social phenomena and contemplate their underlying meanings, thereby fostering their sense of social responsibility and civic awareness. This allows moral education content and English teaching content to permeate each other. Furthermore, the curriculum standards advocate diverse and flexible teaching methods such as situational teaching, cooperative learning, and project-based learning. These methods not only help improve students' English proficiency but also cultivate moral qualities like teamwork and communication skills through practice. By participating in classroom activities and cooperative learning, students learn to respect others, share, cooperate, and form good interpersonal relationships.

Finally, English curriculum evaluation standards also reflect the integration of moral education and English teaching. When evaluating students' English learning outcomes, besides assessing their mastery of linguistic knowledge and skills, attention should also be paid to the moral qualities and emotional attitudes students demonstrate during the learning process. This comprehensive evaluation approach can more fully reflect students' development and provide targeted guidance for their moral education and English learning.

2. Literature Review

International Research Review

International scholars have long studied moral education. For example: Johann Friedrich Herbart placed extremely high value on moral education, positioning "morality" at the core of education. He firmly believed that morality was the ultimate goal of education and the fundamental aim of all educational activities. In exploring moral cultivation, he not only analyzed the natural mechanisms of character formation in detail but also revealed the close connection between intellectual education and moral construction from a psychological perspective, emphasizing the unity of the individual's mind and body. This thinking provides solid theoretical support for the educational concept within subject teaching (Herbart,2015). John Dewey argued that the educational process is essentially a process of moral shaping. He emphasized integrating socially recognized moral values into school curricula within educational practice. This integration not only helps students form correct moral concepts while acquiring knowledge but also guides them to practice moral conduct in real life (Ren,1995).

International scholars generally agree that integrating moral education elements into English teaching is crucial. They believe language is not only a tool for communication but also a carrier for cultural transmission and value dissemination. Therefore, English teaching should not only focus on imparting linguistic knowledge but also emphasize cultivating students' moral character and values.

Domestic Research Review

With the deepening of domestic educational reform, moral education integration in primary school English teaching has gradually become a research focus. Numerous scholars and educators have conducted extensive and in-depth research on this topic. Wang (2014)'s view indicates that deepening the integration of moral education during primary school English teaching not only aligns with contemporary societal expectations but also constitutes a key component of the primary school moral education system. It is the core concept emphasized by primary school English curriculum standards. Such practice holds contemporary significance and reflects the importance of holistic education. When discussing effective methods for moral education integration in primary school English, Yang (2018).

proposed the following strategies: First, he emphasized the importance of environment creation, integrating educational resources from school, family, and society to achieve seamless connection and mutual reinforcement of educational components. Secondly, he proposed situational education, advocating for the close integration of educational content with everyday life scenarios, enabling students to better understand and apply knowledge in practice. Thirdly, he suggested adopting diverse classroom formats, stimulating students' learning initiative and enthusiasm through varied teaching methods. Finally, he mentioned the role of exemplary demonstration, emphasizing that educators should lead by example, setting correct behavioral models for students.

Domestic scholars' recognition of the importance of implementing moral education integration in primary school English teaching continues to strengthen. As research deepens, the diversity of integration methods is increasingly evident. These methods provide valuable references for this paper, effectively avoiding many potential pitfalls in the research process and enabling this study to proceed more efficiently.

3. Method

Literature Review Method

By extensively collecting, organizing, and analyzing relevant domestic and international literature on moral education integration in primary school English teaching, including academic papers and educational monographs, this research gained an in-depth understanding of the current research status, anticipated future trends, and the profound theoretical

foundations in this field. This process not only established a solid theoretical basis for the current research but also clearly defined the research challenges and the overall framework, providing clear direction for subsequent work.

Observational Research Method

By immersing in primary school English classrooms and observing how teachers integrate moral education elements in actual teaching, while recording students' learning performance and reactions, the author gained direct insight into the actual effectiveness of moral education integration in primary school English teaching. This allowed for the collection of first-hand data, providing empirical evidence for subsequent analysis and discussion.

4. Results

Analysis of the Current Situation of Moral Education Integration in Primary School English Teaching

Most teachers prioritize students' examination scores, thereby unintentionally neglecting the integration of moral education content. While this teaching approach might improve English scores in the short term, it may adversely affect students' all-round development in the long run. During their growth, students need not only to acquire knowledge and skills but also to cultivate good moral character and emotional literacy. This excessive focus on scores runs counter to the original purpose of education. Education is not merely about knowledge indoctrination; its core lies in stimulating students' inner potential and prompting them to construct sound outlooks on life, values, and moral concepts. If the integration of moral education is neglected, education itself loses its inherent meaning and value.

Although most teachers acknowledge the importance of moral education in English teaching to some extent, in actual teaching practice, there is a tendency to downplay or overlook its integration. Due to time constraints or a lack of specific methods, they often merely mention moral education content superficially in class, like skimming the surface, without deeply considering how to tightly integrate moral education content with English teaching content.

In selecting methods for moral education integration, teachers lack diversity and innovation. A significant number of teachers overly rely on traditional lecture methods for integration, neglecting other more dynamic and practical approaches. This monotonous method can easily bore students, making it difficult for them to truly internalize moral education content, thereby affecting its effectiveness. Most teachers confine themselves to in-class teaching resources. While this approach can combine moral education content with English teaching, over-reliance on textbooks lacks flexibility and innovation. Few teachers employ a combination of multiple approaches. This indicates that teachers' approaches to moral education integration remain relatively singular, lacking sufficient diversity and comprehensiveness overall.

Causes of Problems in Moral Education Integration in Primary School English Teaching

In primary school English teaching, teachers are not only knowledge transmitters but also guides and role models for students' moral development. As the main agents of moral education integration, their moral awareness and competence directly impact its effectiveness. Firstly, regarding subject knowledge and skills, due to the relative simplicity of English at the primary level, some teachers cease to deepen their knowledge base. Failing to engage in lifelong learning prevents them from improving their own English proficiency. Secondly, influenced by "utilitarian" concepts, teachers prefer to spend time improving students' scores and do not truly recognize the importance of moral education in shaping primary students' worldviews. Lacking relevant training and practice, their integration of moral education becomes superficial, relying on simple, dull classroom preaching. They lack methods and techniques for integration, making it difficult to effectively carry out moral education within English teaching. Furthermore, teachers' words, deeds, values, and attitudes towards life subtly influence students (Ye,2020). If teachers themselves have moral shortcomings, they cannot serve as good role models and may even negatively impact students' moral development.

Moral education evaluation is a crucial means to assess its effectiveness. However, the current evaluation system for moral education within primary school English teaching is still imperfect. Many primary schools lack clear, specific standards for moral education evaluation. This makes it difficult for evaluators to grasp accurately, often leading to subjective and arbitrary evaluation processes, which undermine fairness and accuracy. This not only affects the validity of moral education evaluation but also leaves teachers and students without a clear understanding of the goals and requirements of integration. Moreover, primary school moral education evaluation often relies on traditional written tests and teachers' subjective assessments, resulting in a singular approach. Written tests often overemphasize rote memorization and test-taking skills rather than students' actual demonstration of moral qualities and values. This makes it difficult to comprehensively reflect students' moral development or accurately assess the effectiveness of integration. Furthermore, the results of moral education evaluation are often not utilized effectively. In some schools, evaluation results are merely formal records, not linked to teacher performance appraisals or student advancement evaluations. This reduces the importance teachers and students attach to moral education evaluation and diminishes their enthusiasm and initiative in participating in integration.

In primary school English teaching, moral education integration should be systematic and comprehensive, covering aspects like goals, content, methods, and evaluation. However, existing moral education systems often focus on only one aspect, leading to a lack of cohesion and coordination among the various components of integration, making it difficult to form a synergistic effect. Secondly, primary students of different ages have distinct psychological characteristics and moral development levels. Yet, existing moral education systems are often too generalized, lacking differentiated guidance tailored to different grades. This makes integration difficult to align with students' realities and achieve practical results. Additionally, current moral education systems within primary school English teaching tend to be overly theoretical, lacking specific operational guidance, leaving teachers confused and at a loss when implementing integration.

5. Discussion

5.1 *Capacity Building at the Teacher Level*

5.1.1 Enhance Moral Education Awareness

Enhancing teachers' moral education awareness is key to ensuring the effective implementation of integration. Primary students are in a critical stage of moral concept formation; their moral cognition, emotions, and behavior all require proper guidance and cultivation. English, as a language subject, is not only a tool for communication but also a carrier of culture and values. Teachers should deeply understand the connotation and importance of moral education, truly recognizing it as not only a process of cultivating students' moral character but also a vital pathway for their all-round development. When integrating moral education into English teaching, teachers should avoid focusing excessively on student scores, which renders integration superficial. Instead, they should genuinely integrate moral education concepts into teaching design and practice, ensuring the organic combination of moral and intellectual education.

5.1.2 Master Moral Education Methods

After recognizing the importance of moral education, teachers should master and skillfully apply various moral education methods and approaches to enhance their integration capabilities. Integration can be approached from the following aspects: First, integrate moral education through routine classroom management. Routine management is the foundation for smooth teaching and an important avenue for integration. Teachers should establish clear classroom rules, guiding students to develop good learning and behavioral habits, such as requiring them to observe discipline, respect others, and participate actively in classroom activities. Teachers should continuously emphasize and remind

students of these rules during teaching. Reward and punishment mechanisms can also be used to motivate students to consciously abide by rules, cultivating their self-discipline, collective spirit, and sense of responsibility.

Secondly, uncover moral education materials within teaching content. Primary school English textbooks contain rich moral education resources. Teachers should fully exploit these resources, integrating moral education content into teaching. For example, when teaching vocabulary and phrases, teachers can combine them with relevant moral stories or scenarios to help students understand the moral significance behind the words. When teaching polite expressions, teachers can create situations for students to practice using phrases like "Hello" and "Thank you" in simulated dialogues, thereby cultivating civilized and polite habits. In text teaching, teachers can deeply analyze the content to uncover moral elements such as friendship, honesty, and respect. Through discussions, role-plays, and other activities, students can experience and internalize these moral values through participation, cultivating their moral judgment and sensibilities.

Furthermore, extracurricular practical activities are also important carriers for moral education integration. Teachers can organize various extracurricular activities such as English corners, English competitions, and community service projects, allowing students to exercise abilities and enhance qualities through practice. For instance, in English corner activities, guide students to communicate in English, fostering their communication skills and cooperative spirit. In English competitions, stimulate students' competitive spirit and teamwork, cultivating their resilience and self-confidence. In community service activities, emphasize guiding students to deeply care about social phenomena and actively demonstrate concern for others, thereby fostering their sense of social responsibility and civic awareness. Such activities not only effectively improve students' teamwork skills but also greatly enhance their social interaction abilities, allowing them to experience and understand moral values in practice.

In summary, teachers should comprehensively master and flexibly apply these moral education methods and approaches to ensure moral education content is deeply and effectively integrated into teaching, thereby achieving effective integration, enhancing students' moral character, and promoting their all-round development. Simultaneously, teachers should continuously reflect on and summarize their practical experience in moral education, constantly improving and elevating their own moral education proficiency to better adapt to and meet the demands of integration in primary school English teaching.

5. 1.3 Exemplify Through Words and Actions

Moral education integration is not only an embodiment of teaching philosophy and methods but also a vivid practice of teachers exemplifying through words and actions. Primary students are in a critical period of forming moral concepts and behavioral habits; they are highly imitative and malleable. Teachers' words and deeds have a profound latent influence on students, often silent but powerful. "If a ruler is personally upright, though he does not give orders, they will be carried out; if he is not personally upright, though he gives orders, they will not be obeyed." Therefore, teachers should lead by example, establishing good models of professional ethics, using their own behavior and attitude to influence and nurture students, thereby promoting the continuous improvement and refinement of students' moral character.

In the classroom, teachers should build on a foundation of respect, showing deep care for every student and focusing on their growth and progress. They should create a harmonious, democratic, and equal learning environment, fostering a positively interactive classroom ecology where every student receives adequate attention and opportunity for growth. Outside the classroom, teachers should actively participate in school volunteer activities and social welfare projects, fulfilling social responsibilities and interpreting the true meaning of moral norms through their own actions. They should focus on enhancing their own moral cultivation, ensuring their words match their deeds, leading by example, observing social ethics, professional ethics, and personal integrity, and demonstrating exemplary professional conduct

to set good moral examples for students. This not only helps students form correct moral concepts and behavioral habits but also earns their respect and trust, stimulates their learning interest and motivation, and promotes their all-round development.

5.2 Systematic Support at the School Level

5.2.1 Strengthen Moral Education Training for Teachers

Teachers are the primary implementers of school moral education work; their moral literacy directly affects the effectiveness of integration. By strengthening moral education training, schools can enhance teachers' awareness and capability, helping them update educational concepts, innovate moral education methods, enabling them to more consciously integrate moral education into English teaching and better fulfill their role as models.

Firstly, schools should formulate specific moral education training plans based on actual conditions, ensuring systematicity and effectiveness. Secondly, organize lectures, seminars, and other forms of training, inviting experts, scholars, or experienced teachers. Online resources can also be utilized for e-learning, case sharing, and other activities to enrich teachers' learning pathways. Furthermore, schools should encourage teachers to actively engage in moral education practice within English teaching. Through case analysis and teaching reflection, teachers' practical capabilities can be enhanced. Organizing observation activities for moral education allows teachers to learn from each other and progress together through practice. Finally, schools should incorporate moral education training into the teacher evaluation system, regularly assessing teachers' moral literacy and integration capabilities. Teachers who excel in moral education work should be recognized and rewarded to stimulate their enthusiasm for participation.

5.2.2 Create a Favorable Campus Cultural Atmosphere

Campus culture is a vital component of school education. A favorable campus cultural atmosphere enables students to naturally receive moral education influence in their daily lives. It can subtly influence students' behavioral habits, values, etc., enhancing their comprehensive qualities. It ensures that while mastering subject knowledge, students also develop sound personalities and good moral concepts.

First, schools should focus on improving the overall quality of the campus environment. As an important space students interact with daily, a high-quality environment has a profound positive impact. In constructing the campus environment, the integration of English subject-specific moral education elements should be emphasized. For example, English moral education slogans, famous quotes, and mottos can be posted in prominent campus locations such as corridors and classroom walls, allowing students to receive moral education subtly in their daily lives. These slogans can cover themes like politeness, patriotism, respect for others, and teamwork, such as "Please," "Thank you," "Believe in yourself," helping students develop good behavioral habits and moral qualities imperceptibly.

Secondly, utilize campus radio, television, and other media resources to regularly broadcast English moral education-related stories, songs, speeches, etc., allowing students to feel the power of moral education while watching and listening, and accept moral education in a relaxed and pleasant atmosphere.

Additionally, schools should enrich English subject-specific moral education activities. By organizing diverse activities, students can deeply experience the core values of moral education through participation. For example, hold English class seminars themed on moral construction, allowing students to share their own moral stories and feelings; or establish English corners, organize English moral education speech contests, English writing competitions, English lectures, etc. These activities enable students to showcase their moral education achievements, improve their English skills, and cultivate moral character and social responsibility.

5.2.3 Improve the Moral Education Evaluation Mechanism

First, it is essential to clarify the goals of moral education evaluation. These goals should align with the integration objectives within primary school English teaching, including cultivating students' patriotism, good behavioral habits, teamwork spirit, proactive attitudes, etc. Secondly, to ensure the scientificity and effectiveness of the evaluation mechanism, scientific evaluation criteria must be formulated. These criteria should cover aspects such as students' moral character, behavioral performance, learning attitudes, and cooperative spirit. They should also be designed hierarchically according to students' age characteristics and cognitive levels, ensuring operability and measurability for teachers to evaluate and record effectively. Furthermore, diversified evaluation methods are crucial for comprehensively enhancing students' moral literacy. In addition to traditional teacher evaluation, a multi-agent evaluation model should be actively promoted, encompassing student self-evaluation, peer evaluation, and parental feedback, forming a more comprehensive and objective evaluation system. Encouraging self-evaluation cultivates students' self-awareness and stimulates deep reflection on their learning, enhancing initiative and effectiveness. Peer evaluation fosters mutual understanding and cooperation among students, stimulating participation. Parental evaluation provides valuable perspectives from the family education angle. These methods collectively provide a comprehensive and objective reflection of students' moral development, avoiding the limitations of a single method. Finally, timely feedback is an indispensable part of moral education evaluation. Teachers should regularly provide feedback on evaluation results to students and parents, pointing out strengths and weaknesses and offering specific suggestions for improvement. Simultaneously, teachers should pay attention to students' feedback, promptly adjusting evaluation strategies and methods to ensure moral education evaluation genuinely functions to promote student development.

5.2.4 Strengthen Institutional Safeguards for Moral Education

First, schools should clarify the guiding ideology and basic principles of moral education work. This includes adhering to the principle of placing moral education at the core, ensuring it permeates the entire process of primary school English teaching, guaranteeing the organic combination of moral and intellectual education, etc. It emphasizes the targeted, effective, and operational nature of moral education, enabling it to take root genuinely.

Secondly, establish a sound moral education organizational structure and management system. To ensure the systematicity and efficiency of school moral education work, schools should form a professional moral education leadership team responsible for overall planning, strategy formulation, and guidance. The team should hold regular meetings to deeply analyze emerging trends and challenges in moral education work, propose targeted optimization and improvement plans, and clearly define the moral education responsibilities of various departments, fostering a collaborative environment.

Furthermore, formulate comprehensive moral education rules and regulations. These should include student codes of conduct, reward and punishment systems, teachers' moral education responsibilities, etc., to ensure the standardization and institutionalization of moral education work. Simultaneously, schools should strengthen the dissemination and education of these regulations, ensuring both students and teachers consciously comply and implement them.

Through the implementation of these measures, the effectiveness of moral education integration within primary school English teaching can be safeguarded, laying a solid foundation for students' all-round development.

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